

CONCEPTS ABOUT LANDSCAPES**Allambergenova Arzayım Qudaybergenova**

Republic of Karakalpakstan.

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Abstract. This article describes the concepts of landscapes, the natural landscape and its characteristics.

Keywords: Natural landscape, relief, plant, component.

ПОНЯТИЯ О ЛАНДШАФТАХ

Аннотация. В статье описываются понятия ландшафтов, природного ландшафта и его характеристика.

Ключевые слова: Природный ландшафт, рельеф, растительность, компонент.

A natural landscape is a repetitive combination of the climate, topography, vegetation and soil characteristics of a certain place as a single harmonious unity in certain regions of the earth.

The science that studies the laws of such a combination is landscape science. It is the science of the landscape shell of the earth and its natural elements (natural-territorial and natural-anthropogenic complexes). Along with the concept of "landscape shell", the concepts of natural-territorial complex (THM) and landscape have taken the main place in classical landscape science.

THM is defined as a collection of interrelated natural components (myogenic bases, air climate, water, soil, flora and fauna) in the form of regional compounds at different levels. To date, the concept of "landscape" is interpreted differently. The main thing is to understand the harmony of the landscape with nature, unity, as well as the landscape as a structural element of the landscape shell of the earth, including various rules. Landscapes, legally united in a broad or a certain space, create large physical-geographical systems such as physical-geographic provinces and countries, landscape regions. In turn, the landscapes themselves are composed of several small structural elements - local-scale THMs. The main components of natural regional complexes (geosystems) are natural components as interdependent processes of matter exchange, energies, and information.

Today, it is accepted to group them into three small systems: - geoma - inorganic natural components: lithogenic bases (the upper part of the earth's crust and the relief of the earth's surface), air mass around the earth, natural waters; - biota - flora and fauna; - soil-intermediate or biocomposite (organomineral) subsystem.

Each component has its own characteristics. Usually, material, energetic, and informational are separated separately.

The exchange of matter and energy between its components and parts is based on the interaction and connection of the geospheres that make up the geographic crust and ensure its development. This exchange is in the form of circulation of matter (for example: circulation of water, circulation of chemical elements, biological circulation, etc.). One of the most important features of the geographic crust is its integrity and the fact that it is a complete natural geographic complex. But its unity does not deny the existence of different natural geographical conditions in its different parts.

In other words, the geographic crust itself is a single natural-geographical complex, while it is divided into various large and small natural geographic complexes. These natural-geographical complexes occupy different sizes depending on their size. For example, the largest of them is the geographical crust, the continents and oceans are smaller than it, the natural-geographic regions are even smaller, etc. k. Each of the natural geographic complexes we listed above, including the landscape, is a geosystem. Landscape has a unique scale among geosystems and is a part that forms a certain natural geographical region. At the same time, it is a derivative of a complex and dynamic set of smaller geosystems. Geosystems, including landscapes, are human habitats. They are also a source of many self-renewing natural resources, such as air, water, soil fertility, and biomass, which are necessary for human life. In order for these resources to be replenished and replenished, the exchange of matter and energy in geosystems must be preserved in the same way as it was created by nature. But man tries to create more comfortable and better conditions for his life, to create cultural landscapes that are more productive than natural landscapes. There is no doubt that as human society develops, its influence on nature increases, and the opportunity to change the norms and natural conditions of using natural resources increases. As a result of this, the negative influence of nature on human life and its activities in the economy begins to appear. The imbalance in the relationship between society and nature is causing negative consequences in some places. As a result, the issue of proper use of these existing natural resources, prevention of their poisoning and pollution, comprehensive improvement or efficiency of the environment in which people live has arisen. This issue is an urgent, complex, very diverse, including economic, social, political, cultural and scientific issue that requires multifaceted study.

A positive solution to this issue, in any way, should have a solid scientific basis. Many different sciences, including landscape science, are of special importance in the development of this scientific basis.

Landscape research necessarily requires fieldwork. Landscape research is the only way of natural geographical research used to determine geosystems existing in this or that area.

The landscape maps created as a result of such research will later serve as a clear and reliable scientific basis for the development of various special practical maps, land planning, and the development of measures for nature protection and rational use of natural resources. Another necessary information for applied landscape science is a description that can comprehensively illuminate each landscape complex shown on the universal landscape map. For example, one type of data is needed for agricultural purposes, and another type of data is needed for urban planning. The ability to extract such information correctly and rationally has a direct impact on the results of the work.

In other words, it is necessary to take into account the climate, rocks, topography, soil, water regime, etc. But for agricultural purposes, indicators reflecting certain characteristics of climate or soil are analyzed, while for an engineer engaged in urban planning, indicators reflecting other characteristics become more important. In the process of applying information related to landscapes into practice, there is a need to combine landscapes into groups for a certain purpose, that is, to determine landscape types. Grouping them into some groups based on the impact they have on human activities (construction, reclamation, agrotechnics, etc.) based on the goals of development of one or another branch of the national economy facilitates the practical assessment of landscapes. When developing descriptions for the development of one or another branch of the national economy, it is necessary to take into account the changes that may occur during the natural development of landscapes and the changes that occur as a result of human economic activity. Anticipating (forecasting) whether such changes will occur or not is one of the important issues of applied landscape science. Assessment of landscapes for the purposes of development of the economy or this branch is a direction of applied landscape science.

Therefore, the problem of landscape assessment is one of the main problems of applied landscape science today. The main content of landscape evaluation for one or another purpose is to determine the suitability, convenience or disadvantage of landscapes based on one or another requirements of the individual society. In this regard, three aspects of the evaluation of natural complexes should be clear. First, the object of assessment should be clear. In this case, one of the natural components, for example, climate, terrain, soil or vegetation, can be the object of assessment. But such an assessment is one-sided and cannot provide a comprehensive assessment of the natural conditions of the place. Therefore, it is better to take the geosystem as an object of assessment. The result of the existing evaluation experiments also shows that it is appropriate to consider landscapes as objects. Second, there should be a subject of assessment.

That is, when evaluating natural complexes or landscapes, it should be clear why and for whom it is being evaluated. Agriculture or any of its branches, urban development or any industrial construction, road construction can be taken as a subject.

Third, in addition to the object and subject, the economic geographical, social, natural geographical, scientific and technical conditions at the time of evaluation should also be taken into account. Since the conditions are variable in space and time, the results of the evaluation should be changed accordingly. In other words, the results of evaluation of natural complexes for one or another purpose are relative both in space and time. In order for the results of the landscape assessment to be correct, the main purpose of the assessment should be clearly defined. The main goal of landscape assessment is to determine the appropriate and best options for their development. Appraisals conducted for this purpose are called production appraisals. Another direction in assessment work is the direction of environmental assessment. In it, a person, the population, serves as a subject. The main goal of such an assessment is to create a scientific basis for the correct and rational organization of people's working conditions, rest, and the protection of their health.

This includes the aesthetic assessment of landscapes for recreational purposes. Economic assessment of natural conditions, including landscapes, is one of its unique directions. It can be seen from the published scientific literature that a lot of work has been done in this regard. But the theoretical basis of the economic assessment of natural resources is that in many cases, economists tend to be one-sided in the economic assessment of natural resources and often fail to take into account the natural geographical basis. Therefore, it is appropriate to evaluate the areas in the context of comprehensive landscapes. The natural condition or natural environment that needs to be evaluated is not only a random collection of different natural elements, but also a system in which its parts interact and communicate. This wholeness or oneness is clearly reflected in the landscapes. Assessment of natural conditions for agriculture should begin with the identification of features that may limit the use of landscapes for agriculture.

Such characteristics of landscapes are related to their relief, soils, and the state of underground water. It is expedient that the assessment of landscapes is carried out according to the 3 components considered the most important from the point of view of agriculture: climate, soil, relief, both for irrigated farming and for dry farming. Taking into account that the climate and soil relief can have different effects on the growth and development of agricultural crops, the methods of their evaluation are also different. In the use of landscapes in agriculture, their relief structure is also of great importance.

Based on the evaluation of the relief, it is difficult to get a complete picture of the landscape based on the evaluation of the components without making a general evaluation of the land landscapes. As an object of evaluation, different geosystems are involved in one or another component, one natural resource, for example, minerals, plant resources, land resources, water, etc., and as a subject of evaluation, any branch of the national economy of the society, this or that industrial enterprise, various construction facilities, etc. can serve. Any evaluation results are relative and historical. Because, as a result of the development of social and economic conditions over time, the attitude and demands of the subject to the object may increase.

In addition, it is not always correct to consider any assessment work as a task of applied landscape science. For example, the assessment of an irrigation canal from the point of view of cotton cultivation is a special assessment in the narrow sense. The second direction in assessment is called socio-ecological assessment. In it, landscapes are evaluated in terms of different aspects of human life.

When we evaluate landscapes for one or another purpose, we need to foresee what changes the subject will tend to later and what consequences they may have. It is necessary to predict the changes of landscapes and the consequences of these changes due to the influence of human activities (whether in agriculture, urban development or the construction of a structure). Each component in the landscape is constantly developing and changing, if the characteristic of one of them (for example, climate) changes and acquires a new quality, the remaining components or their characteristic (for example, soil) try to adapt to it. Such a process involves different components with different speed and sometimes a long time. But the first component to change will continue to evolve and change over time. The rest of the components will try to adapt to it again. Therefore, the internal balance in the landscape can be temporary and relative.

Biota (plants and animals) is the most active component of the landscape. It is constantly in conflict with non-biotic components and tries to adapt to the environment. As a result, the entire landscape is reconfigured. Movement and balance are in a constantly changing relationship.

Balance in the landscape can be maintained only in conditions of balance between movement and inactivity in the landscape. But this balance is relative and temporary. If the interactions and contradictions of the components inside the landscape cause the landscape to develop slowly, evenly and without sudden changes, the external influences and relationships can accelerate or change this process. The development of the landscape means the displacement of the signs inherent in its internal structure by the signs of the new content. This process creates qualitative changes in the landscape and leads to the formation of a new landscape. However, in the same landscape, at the same time, signs of the distant past can be found side by side with the

signs typical of the present. In addition, it is necessary to know the history and age of the landscape as well as some events and processes occurring in the landscape at the moment.

Most prediction experiments are based on two major factors. The first of them are natural factors (changes in solar activity, tectonic changes, etc.), and the second are anthropogenic factors, that is, factors related to human economic activity. In regional landscape predictions, it is important to identify the studied region as a whole, and on the other hand, to determine the sustainable directions of the development of dominant landscape types in this region. Therefore, in order to predict the future of landscapes, it is necessary to carry out the analysis of the distribution of landscapes together with the paleogeographic method. . The methods of predicting landscapes are as diverse as the principles. There are more than 50 methods and methods of national predictions.

But not all of them can be usefully used in predicting landscapes. Only some of them can be used. The main reason for this is the complexity and multifactorial nature of geosystems. That is why it is noticeable that geographical methods are mainly used in landscape forecasting experiments. Extrapolation of more practical importance is the selection of geographic similarities, expert assessment, indication, space data analysis, cartographic and other methods. Such a division is conditional, and in practice one method leads to another.

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